

Co-funded by the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Insights from Across Europe: Navigating the Transition to the AI-Powered Online Classroom from Professors' Perspectives, supporting a Pan-European Approach

Gytis Cibulskis, Alberto Hernando Garcia Cervigòn, Marco Montanari, Simona Perone, Miguel Augustos Meneses da Silva Santos

Overview of the transition to online education post-COVID-19

Exploring the evolving perspectives of professors in European universities today

WHAT WE LOOKED FOR

Starting from the ErasmusPlus project **SOULSS** activities

- Investigate professors' perspectives on online education.
- Determine necessary expertise and skills for effective online teaching.
- Offer recommendations for future online education strategies.education.

Teaching Staff
45 questions
8 questions pre-Covid
11 questions post-Covid
13 questions current scenario & general opinions
<i>All multiple-choice questions</i>

Erasmus+

SOULSS

Evolution of Online Education

- Transition from traditional to online education
- Early adoption of online tools and methods
- Influence of technological advancements and pedagogical shifts
- The role of AI today

Present and Future of AI in Linguistics

Linguistics and communication: its interdisciplinary role in supporting all academics' activities

- Artificial General Intelligence (AGI) and Multimodal Models aim to replicate human cognitive abilities across tasks.
- Small Language Models (SLM) and Large Language Models (LLM) demonstrate proficiency in text understanding and generation.
- Future developments in personalized learning, automated tutoring, and real-time assessment.

Broader Educational Transformation

- AI is part of a broader educational transformation.

- Challenges in adapting pedagogical methods
- Leveraging new technologies for student engagement.

Pan-European Collaboration

- Importance of a collaborative approach to online education.
 - Common issues in all Europe:
 - Technological difficulties ('internet connection' and 'adequate computer')
 - Digital skills gaps
 - Difficulty in getting used with new methods
- SOULSS ErasmusPlus Project promotes collaboration and knowledge-sharing among universities.

SOULSS aims

Ongoing Professional Development and Support through a free-to-use Pan European platform to support:

- Importance of continuous skill updates for professors.
- Professional development initiatives to empower professors in online education.

CONCLUSIONS

Key recommendations:

- 1. Support professors in adapting to online education.**
 - 2. Foster collaboration and innovation.**
 - 3. Prioritize professional development and a student-centered approach.**
 - 4. Vision for the future of online education in Europe.**
-

Thank you for your attention!

Contact: marco.montanari@uniroma.it
visit: ww.soulss.eu

WP3 – Conclusions

- The opinion toward remote learning slightly improved across COVID, with a prevalence of positive scores.
However, while teaching staff answers were more homogeneous, a sort of ‘unsatisfaction’ appears among students.
- Remote courses availability and usage slightly increased after COVID-pandemic period. The synchronous modality, and the hybrid one, are the preferred among the remote ones.
- Learning material usage changed for:
 - Paper (decrease)
 - Slides (increase)
 - Video (increase)
 - Interactive material does not receive any particular attention.